

THE MATETICAL-DIDACTIC APPROACH TO PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION AND ITS WAYS OF INVESTIGATION

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Abstract. *This work examines the formation of the competence of self-development, it is necessary to have universal human qualities, love for the country, legal, economic knowledge, the desire for innovation and independent decision-making based on the theoretical knowledge obtained, progressive and innovative development in society. It is important to be aware of changes and learn to use them in everyday life. The selected mathematical content of the student's mathematical preparation on the basis of constructing a graph of the logical structure of three disciplines of the curriculum allows you to organize studies at the level of elementary portions of the educational material*

Keywords: *education, integration, relationships, systematic training, Knowledge, creation, qualities, content, society, development, emergencies, competencies*

Civic duty in the formation of socio-emotional and civic competencies includes knowledge of social and political development, emergencies, environmental problems, as well as understanding of works of art and the development of organizational skills in their preservation. Methodical classes, as the authors write, are, in fact, a system of didactic games, during which children explore problem situations, identify significant signs and relationships, make discoveries. Knowledge is not given in finished form, but through the process of independent discovery by a child of the features and properties of the studied objects and phenomena. A feature of the program is its focus on a deeper study of "objects and phenomena of the world: it prepares children for the perception and elementary understanding of the dialectical unity of the world in its quantitative and qualitative relationships." The authors understand that the necessary condition for successful learning is the creation of a personality-oriented approach to the preschool child, the creation of an atmosphere of goodwill in the educational process.

Consistent and systematic training in intellectual tasks forms the skills and techniques of intellectual activity. In the established practice of teaching, general and special methods of intellectual activity "do not act as objects of special assimilation, their formation proceeds only in the course of assimilation of knowledge and with insufficient control by the educator. Such an organization of learning determines the corresponding course of the process of formation of the main types of mental activity: a great stretch in time, the presence of a variegated variety of intermediate stages, a large spread of the results achieved by individual students. In psychology, this poorly managed process of mastering concepts is actually identified with intellectual development" [7].

In the case of training in intellectual tasks, various types of intellectual activity become the subject of special assimilation. In this case, the main methods of mental activity are formed: recognition, comparison, identification, analysis, synthesis, generalization, analogy, classification, etc. Thus, the formation of intellectual skills provides the development of thought processes

and the mental development of the personality as a whole. The formal-logical side of the methods of mental activity is formed on the material of mathematical content. However, psychologists argue that, being formed on any one subject content, the mental action is further used as a readymade method of thinking in the analysis of any area of reality. The identification of small intellectual (scientific mathematical) problems and the definition of intellectual (scientific) skills as special assimilation not only contributes to the mathematical development of the child, but also outlines a completely new picture of intellectual development as a whole. Oral form of speech:

EXPRESSION AND MEANS

The main qualities that shape oral culture. Literary language norms in oral speech. Accuracy of speech: word usage, pronunciation, word formation, morphological, syntactic norms. Speech accuracy: choosing and using words with a clear understanding of the reality being described. Appropriate use of synonyms, adverbs, antonyms, figurative words.

Working with an excerpt from E. Vahidov's "Slogan of Words". The logic of speech. Be able to articulate the order and structure of ideas. Grammatical tools that make sense. Purity of speech. Sheva's words, barbarism, vulgarism, inactivity and clericalism. The purpose of using them in some situations. Reinforcement lesson Richness of speech, means of its maintenance: Vocabulary, exercises and assignments aimed at knowing the different meanings of words, the appropriate use of synonyms, phrases and figurative expressions and types of conjunctions. Speech fluency. Understand the place, topic, age, social status, and speech situation of the speaker.

Expressiveness of speech. Means of expressiveness: expression, movement, irony and analogy. Work on texts and dictionaries: Oral discussion on "Targeted speech". Work on the text "Do not memorize the topic verbatim", comment on the topic.

WRITTEN FORM OF SPEECH: EXPRESSION AND MEANS

The place of paragraphs in the text. Divide the text into parts. Separating one part of a paragraph from another serves to indicate that a new idea is being expressed through the next part. Work with texts separated by a paragraph and written without a paragraph. Discussion on "My Profession and Written Speech".

Thesis. How is the thesis formed? Where do we start? View resources, collect materials. Write a thesis on any science under the general title "What does it mean". In the process of writing a thesis, in addition to scientific knowledge, to get acquainted with the laws of thesis. Reinforcement lesson. Thoughts in scientific sources, the order of use of facts in the text. Consistency of ideas, comprehensibility, specificity of sentence structure to the laws of the Uzbek language. Abbreviate large text in terms of size, retaining only the most important parts. Small size text extension: "To see how much fuel the driver has left leaned towards the gas station ... "The deceased was twenty-three years old." Rewrite, expand the drab, based on the comments, keeping the content.

LANGUAGE AND THINKING

Where and by whom was this said? Author's word usage skills. Analyze the effect of the selected word on the content and tone. Tasks to determine the effect of words on the tone and content of dramatic and poetic passages. Tasks to identify and evaluate the author's findings (new words, combinations). Be able to compare texts on the same topic written by different authors. The author's choice to create specific parts of the text (for example, the beginning or end of an

event) (for example, comedic, depressing, tragic) Tasks to analyze how the text contributes to the overall structure and content, aesthetics.

The effect of context on the text. The role of context in understanding the text. Exercises to compare texts written on the same topic at different times. "Can you believe it?" Work on a text that provides information on how to verify the accuracy of various information disseminated among social networks and the public. "What images did I have?" prepare a presentation on the topic. Speaking of graphics ... Graphic data. Of information graphical presentation. Ways to present information graphically (diagram, table, graphic organizer). Listen to the audio text on the topic "Red, yellow, green areas" and describe it graphically. Discuss the advantages and disadvantages of graphics and tables in the delivery of information. Word order. The usual order of the parts of speech has changed (inverted) mode. The importance of inversion in speech expression. The order of the words in the passage from the poem "Babur's Harmony", talk about their stylistic feature. Draw conclusions about the order of parts of speech through oral dialogue.

Types of sentences according to the purpose of expression. Do we know our purpose from expressing a sentence? Questions, inquiries, commands and wishes. Their use in speech. How to create a questionnaire. Methodological adaptation of the command sentence.

Listen to the text, differentiate the words in the text according to the purpose of expression. To be able to reinforce the meaning of a command in a sentence, to be able to differentiate a wish from a compound sentence. Explain the means by which a question is formed. Discuss what we use the most in speech.

Rhetorical questioning style. Pure questioning and rhetorical interrogation. Whether rhetorical questions require an answer. Expression of secret affirmation, widely used in journalistic style. Identify question marks from a journalistic text. Classify them according to the expression of pure and rhetorical questioning, identify the means by which the rhetorical question enhances the effectiveness of the sentence. Write an article and use rhetorical questions appropriately. Methodology of contributions. The function of the input. Structure. Simple and complex input. Subjective attitude, complement or identification of information. Applications. Use of punctuation. Read the text, summarize the text. Explain the meaning of the entries in the text. The subject of the speaker's speech that the word expressed is a motivation. The motivation is a reflection of the subjective attitude of the speaker. Use of prompts in speech. The location of the stimuli and their methodological significance. Reading Muhammad Yusuf's poem "A Letter from My Mother", revisiting the lines in which the mother misses. Identify motivations and explain their location. Write a letter to my mother. Methodology of speech inputs. The role of introductions in speech. Their appearance in style. Punctuation. Conjunctive style. Conjunctions with and without conjunctions. The conjunction is active in the spoken form of the compound sentence. Wider use of conjunctions in scientific and formal style. The use of all types of conjunctions in artistic style.

Read a formal, artistic text, think about the style of expression in the text, determine the type of sentences according to their structure, explain the connection of parts of speech. Contemplate this notion as you interact with others. Copywriting and assimilation techniques. An excerpt is a quote from someone else. Parts of speech with excerpts. Don't talk nonsense. The formal changes that occur when a quote is converted into a master sentence.

Punctuation. Analyze the idea understood from the text, turn the quotations into phrases. Exercises and assignments for interpreting shape changes. So, in the basis of the

mathematical development of a preschool child, mathematical knowledge proper can be put. Their selection should be made in accordance with the scientific content of “big mathematics”. A sequence of small portions of educational material aimed at the formation of mathematical knowledge forms a sequence of intellectual (scientific) tasks. In each such task, certain types of intellectual activity become the subject of special assimilation. In accordance with the theory, not only the development of mathematical knowledge occurs, but also specific types of cognitive, mental activity and general educational methods of thinking are formed. This overcomes the gap between the orientation of the preschool child on specific objective methods of action and the installation for the elementary school student of action with abstract mathematical concepts. Children should be taught in small intellectual problems that are adequate to one or another mathematical essence, to one or another image, representation, concept. As a procedural component of mathematical training, a methodological training system has been developed as a source of awareness of the mechanisms of formation of elementary mathematical representations in young children.

The selected mathematical content of the student’s mathematical preparation on the basis of constructing a graph of the logical structure of the three disciplines of the curriculum allows you to organize studies at the level of elementary portions of the educational material. As an objective measure of assessing the quality of knowledge, a test can serve. Obtaining the necessary coefficient of assimilation of knowledge is an objective result (goal) of assimilation of theoretical knowledge, which is specified when organizing control in the traditional way in exams and tests. The real educational process of a pedagogical university considers lectures and classroom practical exercises as the main form of training. Traditional teaching methods are used to organize the educational process in effective didactic systems. A distinctive feature of such an organization is a stable and long-term feedback and directional information process. This is ensured by a system of developed teaching aids, including textbooks and teaching aids; mathematical dictations; notebooks with a printed base; cards of general and individual tasks; graphic and settlement-graphic works; control sections; tests, etc.

Designing an effective educational process using a complete system of developed teaching aids that ensure the teacher’s work in lecture and practical classes in didactic monosystems ensures the assimilation of knowledge at the level of algorithmic activity. To bring the student to the level of creativity, it is necessary to use integrated technology.

The pre-mathematical training carried out in kindergarten is part of the general preparation of children for school and consists in the formation of elementary mathematical representations in them. This process is associated with all aspects of the upbringing and educational work of a kindergarten and is primarily aimed at solving the problems of mental education and mathematical development of preschool children. Its distinctive features are the general developmental orientation, the connection with mental, speech development, gaming, domestic, labor.

When stating and realizing the tasks of pre-mathematical preparation of preschool children, take into account:

- patterns of formation and development of cognitive activity, mental processes and abilities, the personality of the child as a whole;
- age-related opportunities for preschoolers in the assimilation of knowledge and related skills;

- The principle of continuity in the work of kindergarten and school. In the process of pre-mathematical training, educational, educational and developmental tasks are solved in close unity and interconnection with each other.

By acquiring mathematical ideas, the child gains the necessary sensory experience of orientation in the various properties of objects and the relationships between them, masters the methods and techniques of cognition, and applies the knowledge and skills formed during the training in practice. This creates the prerequisites for the emergence of a materialistic outlook, connects learning with the surrounding life, and fosters positive personality traits. Let us dwell on the main tasks of pre-mathematical training of children in kindergarten.

1. Formation of a system of elementary mathematical representations in preschoolers. From the content side, the most important in the sense of the formation of primary simple representations are such fundamental mathematical concepts as “set”, “relation”, “number”, “quantity”. These concepts are widely represented in the initial training, but not in the direct sense, but from the point of view of the propaedeutics of formation, only an idea of them. Figuratively speaking, a child in kindergarten comprehends “sciences before science”, and naturally this is due to the fact that, in their psychological structure, elementary mathematical representations have a figurative nature. The gradual complication of knowledge mastered by children consists in increasing both the volume of quantitative) spatial and temporal representations, and the degree and generalization. The system of knowledge and initial ideas about sets, relationships, numbers and quantities, although it is very limited, by the scope of learning opportunities for preschoolers, is significant for further mastering the concepts of school mathematics. Elementary mathematical representations are formed n; the basis for children to learn in a certain sequence of methods of action (for example, it is proposed to lay out as many objects on a free strip as they are drawn on the sample, to put strips of different lengths on top of each other, pick up pictures with objects to the corresponding geometric figure, etc.) training in the kindergarten, the simplest skills are developed for counting objects, measuring distances, volumes of liquids and bulk solids using conditional standards, and the ability to perform calculations when solving arithmetic problems in one action of addition and subtraction. Elementary mathematical representations and the corresponding methods of action are the main components of the knowledge system for preschoolers. The assimilation of various concepts related to the most complex branches of human knowledge should be based on sensory experience and worldly ideas, which are formed already in preschool age.

The main difference between a concept and a concept is, first of all, that the concept reflects the essential features of an object, abstracted from its other, non-essential properties. The representation reflects both essential and nonessential properties of the object in its direct perception. In experimental studies (P. Ya. Halperin, L.F. Obukhova, etc.), the possibility of the formation of separate full-fledged mathematical concepts in preschoolers is shown, but this requires special conditions. Consider some conditions under which the assimilation of concepts and the development of conceptual thinking are possible.

A conceptual way of recognizing objects is possible based on the method of phased formation of mental actions (P. Ya. Halperin). This method is a certain sequence of actions: knowing the essential sign of the concept-104, the child identifies the properties of the subject in question and compares them with the essential sign of the concept, and then concludes whether the analyzed object belongs to this concept or not. First, the comparison of signs occurs mod the

guidance of the teacher. Then the child himself, comparing the signs, reasoning out loud. At the next stage, comparing these signs, he reasons mentally, "to himself", according to the same scheme, which serves as the basis for speech. So, gradually, assimilating the sequence of actions reflected in the external and then internal speech, the child masters the way of bringing any object, property or phenomenon under study. A detailed judgment according to the pattern of actions taken gradually passes first into a plan of short speech "to oneself", and then into a plan of mental action. Now, having mastered the mode of action and reasoning, the child will be able to solve any new problem on his own.

Learning, built on the method of phased development of mental actions, allows you to get closer to the formation of the concept of number, based on an understanding of the principle of maintaining volume, mass and quantity, to create the basis for the emergence of elements of theoretical thinking (L. F. Obukhova).

Increasing the level in the generalization of mathematical representations, the formation of mathematical concepts is promoted not only by the special organization of mental activity, but also by the use of special cognitive tools in the learning process: models, graphs, diagrams, etc. For example, a "ladder" made up of circles models cardinal and ordinal relations of natural numbers, four circles - pink, white, blue and black - model parts of the day and so on. formation of elementary mathematical concepts in preschool children. It may be implemented in different ways. Since the experience and knowledge of children is small, training basically goes like this: first, with the help of an adult, specific knowledge is accumulated, and then they are generalized to the simplest rules and patterns. However, this necessary and important path for the mental development of young children also has its drawbacks: children cannot go beyond those isolated facts and cases on the basis of which they were summarized to generalizations; unable to analyze a wider range of knowledge, which limits the development of their independent thoughts and searches. Therefore, in teaching it is necessary to use another way, when thought and assimilation of knowledge go from general to particular. The learned rule, children must learn to apply in specific conditions.

1. A rational combination of these methods contributes to the highest mental and mathematical development of children. It is not always necessary to put a child in the position of a "discoverer", to lead him from single concrete knowledge to conclusions and generalizations. The child must learn to master and acquire the ready-made knowledge accumulated by mankind, value it, be able to use it to analyze both their experience and the facts and phenomena of life around them. For example, at a certain stage, preschoolers are introduced to quadrangles. Turning to children's experience, one can first propose to find and name those familiar figures that have four sides and four corners and can be assigned to quadrangles, and secondly, to find objects or parts of objects of a quadrangular shape (this concretization deepens knowledge children about this geometric figure).

Similarly, children are introduced to polygons. Concretizing their knowledge, preschoolers show and name triangles, squares, rectangles of different sizes, relating all these figures to polygons. The idea of a polygon, as it were, is built up over the whole variety of figures, limited by closed broken lines, right and wrong, large and small. Therefore, for the development of children's mental abilities, it is necessary to use different ways, to bring them to understanding the unity of the general and the individual, the abstract and the concrete. Education in kindergarten is not only a communication of knowledge, but also the development of children's mental abilities,

mechanisms of mental activity, which facilitates the transition from empirical knowledge to conceptual.

2. The formation of the prerequisites of mathematical thinking and individual logical structures necessary for mastering mathematics in school and general mental development. Mastering the initial mathematical concepts contributes to the improvement of the cognitive activity of the child as a whole and its individual sides, processes, operations, actions. The formation of the logical structures of thinking - classification, ordering, understanding the preservation of quantity, volume mass, etc., acts as an important independent feature of the general mental and mathematical development of a preschool child.

The process of forming elementary mathematical representations is built taking into account the level of development of a visual-effective and visual figurative thinking of a preschooler and has as its goal the creation of prerequisites for the transition to more abstract forms of orientation in the environment. Mastering various practical ways of comparing, grouping objects by quantity, size, shape, spatial location actually lays the foundation for logical thinking. In the process of forming mathematical representations, preschoolers develop the ability to use indirect methods to evaluate various properties of objects (counting to determine quantity, measurement to determine quantities, etc.), anticipate the result, judge the initial data by the result, understand not only visible external relations and dependencies, but also some internal, the most significant. A definite result of the education of preschoolers is not only the formed system of mathematical representations, but also the foundations of visual-schematic thinking as a transitional stage from concrete to abstract. In children, the ability to analytic-synthetic and classifying activities, abstracting and generalizing is improving.

3. The formation of sensory processes and abilities. The main direction in teaching young children is the implementation of a gradual transition from specific, empirical knowledge to a more general one. Empirical knowledge formed on the basis of sensory experience is a prerequisite and necessary condition for the mental and mathematical development of preschool children. Already in early childhood, ideas about the environment, about the signs and properties of the objective world begin to take shape: the shape, size, spatial arrangement of objects and their quantity. The basis for young children to learn about the qualitative and quantitative signs of objects and phenomena is based on sensory processes: sensation, perception, and representation. The kid learns the properties and qualities of the subject in actions, in a practical way. "The closet is behind you," they say to the child. "And where is it from behind: where is the back?" - the child specifies and presses his back to the closet in order to specifically feel, to know the spatial position of the object behind.

"Find among the toys those that look like this triangle." The child, having carefully examined the triangle and examined it with his hands, quite easily searches for objects similar to a given shape. Children are purposefully taught certain techniques and generalized methods of examination: tracing an object's contour with a hand and looking to identify the shape, "weighing" objects on the palms of both hands in order to compare their masses, applying or applying strips of paper to compare lengths, comparing elements of one group of objects with another to clarify the relationships "more", "less", "equal", etc. This is a comparison in form, size, quantity, comparison of the revealed signs with what is already in the child's experience.

A higher level of orientation in quantitative, spatial and temporal relations is ensured by the ability to use generally accepted standards. The system of standards has developed in the socio-historical practice of man and represents ordered forms (geometric figures), values (measures of length, mass, volume, time, etc.) and other qualities. By mastering this kind of knowledge, the child gets a set of standards, or standards, with which he can compare any newly perceived quality, find him a place among others.

In preschool age, the development of sensory standards is carried out not only at the perceptual, but also at the intellectual level (L. A. Wenger). Young children master the individual elements of the system of standards, using the survey activities that adults taught them. Older preschoolers, using classification, come to the realization of the principle of constructing such systems. The work on the development and use by children of sensory standards in kindergarten is just beginning, a deeper familiarization with them takes place at school.

Sensory processes (perception, representation) and abilities (observation, eye) are also the basis of focused work carried out with children in line with their pre-mathematical training. A special organization of sensory experience creates the basis for indirect knowledge, prepares for the formation of mathematical concepts.

4. Expanding the vocabulary of children and improving coherent speech. The process of forming elementary mathematical representations involves the systematic assimilation and gradual expansion of the vocabulary, improving the grammatical structure and connectedness of speech. With the help of words, a child reflects quantitative relations with many, one, not one, so many, how many, equally, more, less, etc., which are recognized as a result of direct actions when comparing individual objects and their aggregates. Borrowed from the speech of others, the numeral words are filled with meaning and are used for a specific purpose - to find out how many objects. When counting, the child learns on an intuitive level to coordinate the numeral with the noun in gender, number and case. Comparison of collections of objects by quantity, and later comparison of numbers requires the construction and use of rather complex speech structures. Not only the results of cognitive activity are clothed in a speech form, but also its methods. The child is required to tell what he did (for example, put 6 red circles on the top strip and 7 blue ones on the bottom) and what happened (there were more blue circles than red ones and red ones less than blue ones). The deeper the mathematical relationships, dependencies and relationships are realized, the more advanced tools are used to reflect them in speech.

Conclusion. The general secondary education system provides for the formation of basic competencies in the student, along with scientific competencies. It consists of the formation of basic competencies for self-development, the ability to apply the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in different situations, based on the knowledge acquired by the student through the subjects of the block of language and literature. In particular, it is necessary to develop the skills of applying the knowledge of the native language in the process of communication in the formation of communicative competencies, the formation of skills of independent, creative thinking, written and oral fluency in the state language and foreign languages.

There is a need for regular use of modern information and telecommunications tools, which expand the opportunities for the effective development of information competence in the teaching of science. It is recommended that students use mobile devices (phones, tablets, and other gadgets) to develop the skills of searching for, analyzing, and analyzing information about science from a variety of sources, and working with information while maintaining information security.

In the formation of self-development competence to have universal qualities, love of country, legal, economic knowledge, aspiration to innovation and independent decision-making on the basis of acquired theoretical knowledge, progressive and innovative development in society. It is important to be aware of changes and learn to use them in everyday life. Civic duty in the formation of socio-emotional and civic competencies includes knowledge of social and political development, emergencies, environmental problems, as well as understanding of works of art and the development of organizational skills in their preservation. The concept of development of preschool education and training is the most important component of the modernization of the national system of preschool education, due to a number of factors:

- updating the role and purpose of preschool education in the system of continuing education;
- updating goals, objectives, principles, approaches, priorities in the system of preschool education;
- A new vision of the key results of preschool education;
- transition to a competency-based model of preschool education.

This Concept outlined the strategic guidelines for the development of preschool education and training, following which will contribute to:

- improving the resource support of the process of education and training of preschool children (financial, material, technical, personnel, software, scientific and methodological, technological);
- modeling of a high-quality, developing, health-saving, sociocultural environment in preschool organizations;
- technologization of the educational process in preschool organizations;
- achieving the quality of preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Foreign language lesson has its own specificity, unlike other school subjects; the main objective of a foreign language lesson is the formation of intercultural communicative competence of learners. At the present moment the global aim of teaching foreign language is involvement to other culture and participation in dialogue of cultures. This aim is gained by the way of formation the ability to intercultural communication. The process of teaching foreign language is organized on the basis of communicative character tasks; teaching foreign language communication using all necessary for this work means is a distinctive feature of a foreign language lesson.

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